

Short communication

BAPTRIA TIBIALE (ESPER, 1804) (LEPIDOPTERA: GEOMETRIDAE), A NEW GENUS AND SPECIES FOR THE FAUNA OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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The moth fauna of Bosnia and Herzegovina in European terms can be regarded as one of the least studied. Most of the existing data are based on historical records (Rebel, 1904) with only a limited number of new records (Hanjalić & Lelo, 2015; Koren & Kulijer, 2020; Koren & Martinović, 2020; Koren & Zadravec, 2016; Plóciennik *et al.*, 2007, Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021). This is true both in terms of published moth surveys as well as available datasets in online databases and similar resources. Thus, even for some of the best studied moth families, such as Geometridae, the distribution maps of many species for the country are empty or with a very small number of records (Hausmann, 2001; Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). Accordingly, many new species are expected to be recorded in the future.

Here we present the first record of a rare moth, *Baptria tibiale* (Esper, 1804), for Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The survey was conducted in the period from 16th June to 4th July 2021 on the territory of Blidinje Nature Park and its surroundings in the high mountain area of northern Herzegovina (Fig. 1), as part of a regional collaboration in biodiversity research and the development of Biologer, an open platform for collecting biodiversity data in southeastern Europe (Popović *et al.*, 2020). Only a single specimen of *B. tibiale* was collected during this study.

Examined material: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kukavice, east banks of Kukavičko Lake (Fig. 2A), 43° 57' 2" N, 17° 19' 58" E, 02.07.2021, 1 ♂, leg. M. Martinović, (Fig. 2B).

Figure 1. Map of Bosnia and Herzegovina with the locality marked where *B. tibiale* was collected.

Figure 2. A – Habitat at Kukavičko Lake where *B. tibiale* was recorded; B – *Baptria tibiale* from Kukavičko Lake, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

B. tibiale is a boreo-montane species with Palearctic distribution (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). In Europe it occurs in fragmented populations from the Alps to the Carpathians and from northern Europe to the Urals (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). In the distribution maps given in The Geometrid Moths of Europe series of

books, only two points are found in the Balkans, one from Montenegro and the other from Bulgaria (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). The closest records to the one in Bosnia and Herzegovina are from central Croatia, recorded in 1918 (Mihoci, 2012), and Montenegro (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). No additional records from Croatia or Montenegro are known to the authors. Seemingly, *B. tibiale* is a rare and very local species in southeastern Europe. This record from Bosnia and Herzegovina fills a distributional gap between Croatia and Montenegro, and more importantly, indicates the possibility of discovering new populations of this beautiful species.

The caterpillars of this species are monophagous and feed on *Actaea* spp. (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). In general this species can be characterized as mesophilic to hygrophilic (Macek, 2007).

Baptria tibiale is an easily recognizable Geometridae species, with black wings and a white streak on the inner side of the upper wings. The species is diurnal and usually flies in the canopies of trees (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012). This may be the reason there are so few historical records from the area, as well as the fact that there are very few Lepidoptera experts and enthusiasts collecting moth data in the region.

Future surveys of the species will most likely provide further records in other localities, and even in neighboring countries.

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BAPTRIA TIBIALE (ESPER, 1791) (LEPIDOPTERA: GEOMETRIDAE), НОВИ РОД И НОВА ВРСТА ЗА ФАУНУ БОСНЕ И ХЕРЦЕГОВИНЕ

ТОНИ КОРЕН, ДЕЈАН КУЛИЈЕР И МАТЕА МАРТИНОВИЋ

Извод

У овом раду је представљен први налаз ретког ноћног лептира, *Baptria tibiale* (Esper, 1804), за фауну Босне и Херцеговине. Врста је забележена на Кукавичком језеру у западној Босни 02.07.2021. године.

B. tibiale је борео-монтанска врста, распрострањена у Палеарктику. Она је ретка и веома локална у југоисточној Европи. Распрострањена је од Алпа до Карпата и од северне Европе до Урала, а најближи налази потичу из централне Хрватске и из Црне Горе.

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